

Engineering Atomizers for Intensified Carbon Capture: A Comparative Performance Study

Frantisek Lizal¹; Ondrej Cejpek¹; Milan Maly¹; Miloslav Belka¹; Ondrej Hajek¹; Jiri Hajek¹, Jan
Jedelsky¹

*¹Brno University of Technology, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Energy Institute, Technicka
2896/2 Brno, 616 69, the Czech Republic*

Abstract:

Efficient Post-Combustion Carbon Capture (PCC) requires process intensification, realized by optimizing mass transfer at the gas-liquid interface. Within spray-column contactors, atomizers play a crucial role in this effort, yet a systematic engineering framework for their design, selection, and performance comparison under PCC-relevant conditions remains a significant gap. This study addresses this by designing, fabricating, and experimentally evaluating seven diverse single-fluid and twin-fluid atomizer types. A novel comparative methodology was employed, ensuring all atomizers were assessed under identical liquid flow rates and matched total energy input levels, enabling an unbiased and application-focused performance analysis across key metrics: droplet size distribution (DSD) uniformity, spray cone angle (SCA), atomization efficiency (η_A), specific energy consumption, and entrainment risk (IV_e). Our findings provide design guidance for intensified PCC. Optimized single-fluid atomizers (e.g., SH, FF, HC, FC) demonstrated superior energy efficiency ($\eta_A > 2\%$, specific energy < 300 J/kg), representing a threefold improvement over typical twin-fluid designs, while maintaining low entrainment risk ($IV_e < 5\%$) and robust operation. In contrast, twin-fluid atomizers (EFF, IMP) achieved the finest droplets but at significantly higher energy penalties (up to 900 J/kg) and substantial entrainment risk (up to 30%), rendering them less suitable for large-scale PCC without extensive downstream separation. Crucially, the study also validates a methodology for engineering atomizer

24 geometry to achieve specific SCA independent of flow rate, offering better control for reactor
25 optimization. This work delivers essential data and a validated, application-driven design methodology
26 to accelerate the development of compact, energy-efficient, and sustainable spray-column PCC
27 systems.

28 **1. Introduction**

29 The drive for more sustainable and energy-efficient chemical processes has placed renewed focus on
30 the design of novel equipment capable of delivering step-changes in performance. Post-combustion
31 carbon capture (PCC) is a critical technology for mitigating CO₂ emissions from industrial processes
32 reliant on fossil fuels. Among various PCC technologies, spray columns offer an attractive solution due
33 to their simple construction, scalability, and low pressure drop. The performance of these columns is
34 fundamentally governed by the liquid atomizer, which disperses the chemical sorbent, typically an
35 amine solution, into fine droplets to maximize the interfacial area for mass transfer. The choice and
36 performance of the atomizer thus represent a primary engineering control point where targeted
37 hardware design can yield substantial gains in overall process efficiency.

38 Effective atomization requires achieving a specific droplet size distribution (DSD); droplets must be
39 small enough to provide a large surface area for efficient CO₂ absorption but large enough to prevent
40 being carried out of the column by the flue gas, a phenomenon known as entrainment which leads to
41 sorbent loss and negative environmental impact (Fang et al. 2020; Cho et al. 2018; Belka et al. 2025).
42 Achieving an optimal, narrow DSD is therefore a key challenge in spray column design and a primary
43 barrier to maximizing the performance of this unit operation.

44 Despite the critical role of atomizers, a comprehensive and systematic comparative study under
45 application-relevant, identical operating conditions remains conspicuously absent. The review of
46 existing literature shows that various atomizer types (see Figure A1) have been employed in laboratory
47 and pilot-scale studies (summarized in Table A1). However, comparison of the performance of the used

48 atomizers is virtually impossible due to varying dimensions, velocities, flow rates, evaluation metrics,
49 methodologies, materials of the atomizers, and also different focuses of the respective studies. While
50 a few authors have concentrated on spray characteristics and even fewer on their direct link to
51 absorption, the data lack the consistency required for robust engineering design. Nonetheless, the
52 review revealed the general prevalence of pressure swirl atomizers (Full Cone or Hollow Cone), while
53 other types like effervescent or showerhead atomizers are less frequently reported, although some
54 authors presented convincing arguments for their wider application (Cho et al. 2018). This fragmented
55 landscape underscores the need for a unified approach to characterize and compare atomizer
56 performance, informing the selection of optimal devices for carbon capture spray columns.

57 This study addresses the above-mentioned shortcomings through a combination of application-
58 specific hardware design and a comparative performance analysis. First, to overcome the limitations
59 of standard components, we designed and fabricated a set of the most suitable types of atomizers for
60 PCC. The primary design objective was to tune the properties of atomizers to the identical input
61 conditions to facilitate their meaningful comparison, and, where possible, also to decouple the *SCA*
62 from the liquid flow rate, enabling enhanced control over the spray geometry to better match specific
63 reactor conditions. Second, we conducted the performance analysis, benchmarking these custom-
64 designed atomizers in controlled laboratory conditions. To ensure an unbiased comparison, all
65 atomizers were operated at matched total energy input levels. Performance was evaluated based on
66 key metrics, including the Integral Sauter Mean Diameter (ID_{32}), DSD uniformity represented by the
67 Integral Relative Span Factor (*IRSF*), *SCA*, atomization efficiency (η_A), and the potential for sorbent loss
68 via entrainment expressed by the Integral Volume of Entrainment (IV_e).

69 While the target application involves atomization of amine solutions (to name at least the most
70 prominent: MEA, diethanolamine, methyldiethanolamine, sterically hindered amines, piperazine, or
71 blended amines), experiments were conducted with water, whose physical properties at 20°C are
72 similar to those of 30% MEA at a typical operating temperature of 40°C, to minimize environmental

73 and safety hazards. As our main focus is engineering design and comparison of atomization
74 performance, using a surrogate liquid does not interfere with these goals and is justifiable, especially
75 considering the need for fair comparison using one liquid on one hand and the wide range of possible
76 absorbents in real life on the other.

77 The novelty of this work thus lies in the systematic and fair comparison of the broad range of design-
78 optimized atomizers at matched energy input levels and with complex metrics encompassing all the
79 important spray and droplet characteristics. The resulting dataset provides a unique guide for atomizer
80 selection and also presents a validated methodology for application-specific hardware design, paving
81 the way for the development of cleaner and more energy-efficient spray-column carbon capture
82 systems.

83 **2. Methods**

84 A total of seven distinct custom-designed atomizer configurations were analyzed, comprising both
85 single-fluid and twin-fluid types. These included two hollow-cone (HC) series, a full-cone (FC), a flat-
86 fan (FF), a showerhead (SH), an effervescent (EFF), and an impinging effervescent (IMP) atomizer.
87 Schematics of the atomizer designs are shown in Figure 1 and Figure A2 in the attachment. The critical
88 dimensions are shown in Table 1 and explained in the following section.

89 Not to scale

90 Fig. 1. Schemes of the atomizers compared within this study: (a) flat fan (FF), (b) hollow cone (HC), (c)

91 full cone (FC), (d) effervescent (EFF), (e) impinging effervescent (IMP). TIP - tangential inlet ports, Sch -

92 swirl chamber, AC - air core, DO - discharge orifice, LS - liquid sheet. The typical spray pattern is shown

93 below.

94

95

96 2.1. Design and Optimization of Atomizers

97 The design of all atomizers was based on rules established in the literature, which are detailed below
98 for each configuration. The reason why custom-designed atomizers were fabricated instead of simply
99 using the off-the-shelf products was to keep the identical material and production methods to
100 maintain the material and surface properties. Moreover, within the design phase, the performance of
101 each type of atomizer could be fine-tuned in an iterative process to ensure the best-performing
102 geometry was selected for the comparison. All atomizers were designed to yield a maximum SCA of
103 40° to reduce the amount of liquid adhering to the test section walls.

104 The design of the HC atomizers uses the atomizer constant (K), defined as the ratio of the inlet port
105 area to the product of the swirl chamber and orifice diameters ($A_p / (d_s \cdot d_o)$) (Nural and Ertunç, 2018).
106 According to Rizk and Lefebvre (1986), the SCA of HC atomizers is proportional to the atomizer constant
107 K , as described by Equation 1.

$$SCA = 6K^{-0.15} \left(\frac{\Delta p_L d_0^2 \rho_L}{\mu_L^2} \right)^{0.11}, \quad (1)$$

108 where p_L is the liquid inlet pressure, ρ_L is the liquid density, and μ_L is the viscosity of the liquid.

109 Four geometric variants of each HC atomizer series were produced. The HC-B series was designed with
110 a constant K value of 1.88. The HC-A series was initially designed with $K = 2.40$. However, due to
111 insufficient spray development at low pressures recognized during the trial tests, the final four
112 geometric variants of the HC-A series were designed with distinct atomizer constants ($K = 2.28, 2.31,$
113 $2.40,$ and 2.40) to ensure stable spray formation at their respective nominal operating pressures of 25,
114 50, 100, and 200 kPa.

115 The FC atomizers feature an orifice at the rear side of the swirl chamber, which increases axial
116 momentum and results in a lower SCA compared to HC atomizers.
117 Dimensions of FC atomizers were determined iteratively, on the basis of HC atomizers' dimensions.
118 The FF atomizer design was based on principles shown in (Chen et al. 2022; Kashani et al. 2018), and
119 details of the specific design and testing are in (Cejpek et al. 2024).

120 For effervescent atomizers, the geometry has a limited impact on the SCA, which is mainly governed
121 by the gas-to-liquid ratio (*GLR*) and inlet pressure. In impinging effervescent atomization, the SCA is, in
122 addition, also affected by the angle of the exit orifices (Cejpek et al. 2023).

123 All atomizers were fabricated using stereolithography 3D printing on a 9K printer (Elegoo, Shenzhen,
124 China) with a resolution of 18 μm in the XY plane and 50 μm along the Z-axis. The material used was
125 Siraya Tech Build High Resolution (Richvsky manufacturing s.r.o., Hodonin, the Czech Republic), a
126 technical resin selected based on prior testing of various resins, in which it demonstrated the best
127 performance. After printing, the atomizers were thoroughly rinsed several times with isopropyl alcohol
128 and then dried with compressed air to remove any residual uncured resin. Finally, the atomizers were
129 cured in a post-curing station using 48 W UV light with a wavelength of 405 nm for a duration of
130 2 minutes.

131 **2.2. Experimental Setup and Operating Conditions**

132 All experiments were conducted on a dedicated test facility (Figure 2) equipped with a computer-
133 controlled 3D traverse mechanism for precise atomizer positioning (positioning error < 0.1 mm).

134

135 *Fig. 2. The scheme of the experimental setup for atomizer characterization.*

136 For single-fluid atomizers, water was supplied from a pressurized tank, with the flow rate measured
 137 by a Coriolis mass flow meter (Mass 2100 Di3, Siemens AG, 0.1% accuracy from actual value) and inlet
 138 pressure monitored by a piezo-resistive sensor (DMP 331i, BDsensors s.r.o., uncertainty of 1.5 kPa).
 139 For twin-fluid atomizers, filtered air was supplied from a reservoir, with its flow rate measured by a
 140 mass flow meter (FMA-A2100, Omega Engineering, $\pm 1\%$ accuracy from full scale) and pressure
 141 measured by a similar piezo-resistive sensor. As mentioned earlier, to minimize environmental and
 142 safety hazards, the experiments were conducted using water as a surrogate for real sorbents. The fact
 143 that the physical properties of water at 20 °C are similar to MEA at 40 °C (which, however, also depends
 144 on the concentration of MEA and CO₂ loading, Amundsen et al. 2009) allows for a meaningful
 145 comparison of atomizer performance.

146 *Table 1. Dimensions and inlet liquid and air pressures for all the compared atomizers. The symbols*
 147 *correspond to Figure 1.*

Atomizer	d_s [mm]	d_o [mm]	l_o [mm]	l_s [mm]	h_p [mm]	b_p [mm]	d_r [mm]	p_L [kPa]	p_g [kPa]
HC-A1	4.7	3.0	1.3	5.2	3.6	3.0	0	23	0
HC-A2	4.0	2.5	1.1	4.3	3.0	2.5	0	48	0
HC-A3	3.2	2.1	1.0	3.7	2.6	2.1	0	98	0
HC-A4	2.7	1.8	0.8	3.1	2.2	1.8	0	191	0
HC-B1	6.0	3.2	1.4	5.4	3.8	3.15	0	27	0
HC-B2	5.1	2.7	1.2	4.5	3.2	2.65	0	54	0

HC-B3	4.3	2.25	1	3.9	2.7	2.25	0	102	0
HC-B4	3.6	1.9	0.8	3.2	2.3	1.9	0	182	0
FC-1	7	2.85	1.3	5.6	3.6	3.0	2.4	23	0
FC-2	4.4	2.3	1.0	4.5	2.9	2.4	2.0	51	0
FC-3	3.7	1.95	0.8	3.8	2.3	2.0	1.7	93	0
FC-4	3.1	1.6	0.7	3.2	2.0	1.7	1.4	194	0
	a [mm]	b [mm]	c [mm]	d [mm]	α [°]				
FF-1	4.3	0.8	2.5	0.65	30			20	0
FF-2	4.73	0.88	2.75	0.715	30			53	0
FF-3	6.88	1.28	4	1.040	30			98	0
	d_o [mm]	d_m [mm]	l_m [mm]	θ [°]					
IMP-1	2.6	15	48	15				21	23
IMP-2	3.4	15	48	15				14	20
IMP-3	3.0	15	48	15				10	13
IMP-4	4.14	15	48	15				4	10
EFF-2.5GLR-1	7	15	48	-				11	14
EFF-2.5GLR-2	5.5	15	48	-				16	18
EFF-5GLR-1	11	15	48	-				4	10
EFF-5GLR-2	7	15	48	-				10	16
SH	$d_o = 0.15$ mm; number of holes = 720; head diameter = 196 mm							40	0

148 All atomizers were operated to maintain a constant liquid flow rate of 140 kg/h. This was done to
149 simulate the same liquid-to-gas flow rate conditions inside the column, which was previously found to
150 have the largest effect on CO₂ capture efficiency (Lim et al. 2013; Niu et al. 2010; Qing et al, 2011). To
151 ensure an unbiased comparison between single- and twin-fluid types, operating pressures were
152 selected to provide identical total energy input, E , for each measurement point, calculated according
153 to Eq. (7). The corresponding specific operating conditions for each test are detailed in Table 1.

154 Droplet size, velocity, and spray geometry were characterized using a high-speed imaging system. A
155 FASTCAM SA-Z camera (Photron, Japan) coupled with a NAVITAR 12X Zoom long-distance microscope
156 was used to capture images of liquid discharge and spray droplets. For droplet size analysis, images
157 were acquired 200 mm downstream of the atomizer at multiple radial positions ranging from
158 ± 105 mm (windows shown as area “II” in Figure 2). The image resolution was 1024 × 1024 px with a
159 field of view of approximately 6 × 6 mm. This resulted in the resolution of 175 px/mm and the smallest
160 detectable droplet of approximately 20 μ m. The camera frame rate was set to 250 fps with a shutter

161 speed of 2.5 μs . For SCA and discharge velocity analysis, images were recorded at the atomizer exit
162 orifice with a frame rate of 20,000 fps and shutter speed of 2.5 μs (area “I” in Figure 2). The field of
163 view was approximately 18 \times 18 mm. The total number of images for each measurement was 1500.
164 Illumination was in both cases provided by a pulsed high-power LED with a pulse duration of 600 ns
165 (HPL3-36DD18B, Lightspeed Technologies, USA).

166 The in-house MATLAB code described in Cejpek et al. 2025 was used for droplet detection. This code
167 binarizes images and calculates equivalent droplet diameters from the area of sharp, in-focus droplets
168 (Figure 3). The filtering of out-of-focus blurry droplets within the code (based on boundary gradient
169 thresholds) effectively minimizes out-of-plane sizing errors. The description and validation of this
170 approach were presented in Maly et al. 2019 and Cejpek et al. 2025. The paper of Maly et al. 2019 also
171 contains details on the second in-house MATLAB code used in this study for the extraction of SCA.

172

173 *Fig. 3. Captured droplet image and its binarization for subsequent droplet detection.*

174 **2.3. Data Analysis and Performance Metrics**

175 The following metrics were used to quantify atomizer performance. The ID_{32} , which represents the
176 volume-to-surface area ratio of the entire spray, was calculated according to Jedelsky et al. (2009):

$$ID_{32} = \frac{\sum r_i f_i D_{i,30}^3}{\sum r_i f_i D_{i,20}^2}, \quad (2)$$

177 where $D_{i,30}$ and $D_{i,20}$ are the diameters of average mass and surface, respectively, f_i is the measured
 178 data rate, and r_i is the radial position of the i -th measurement.

179 The uniformity of the droplet size distribution was quantified by the *IRSF*. This metric, which integrates
 180 measurements performed in several radial positions, was selected to ensure a representative sampling
 181 of the whole spray.

$$IRSF = \frac{\sum r_i f_i RSF_i}{\sum r_i f_i}, \quad (3)$$

182 where $RSF_i = (d_{v0.9,i} - d_{v0.1,i}) / d_{v0.5,i}$, and $d_{v0.1,i}$ is 10% volume diameter, $d_{v0.5,i}$ is 50% volume diameter, and
 183 $d_{v0.9,i}$ is 90% volume diameter in the i -th position.

184 The discharge coefficient (C_d) was calculated using Equation (4) for all atomizers except FF. It is an
 185 important parameter indicating the throughput of the liquid. The C_d is defined as the ratio of the actual
 186 mass flow rate through the atomizer to the theoretical mass flow rate if there were no losses. For FF
 187 atomizers, where the precise determination of the exit orifice area is challenging, C_d can be calculated
 188 using Equation (5).

$$C_d = \frac{\dot{m}}{A\sqrt{2\rho_L p_L}}, \quad (4)$$

$$C_d = u_L \sqrt{\frac{\rho_L}{2p_L}}, \quad (5)$$

189 where \dot{m} is the liquid mass flow rate, A is the exit orifice area, u_L is the liquid velocity, ρ_L is the liquid
190 density, and p_L is the liquid inlet pressure (Pa).

191 The atomization efficiency η_A can be calculated according to (Jedelsky and Jicha 2013) from Equation
192 (6), where σ is the surface tension, E is the input energy (see eq. (7)), and V_L is the liquid volume.

$$\eta_A = \frac{6\sigma}{\frac{E}{V_L} ID_{32}} \quad (6)$$

193 The inlet pressure ranges for the twin-fluid atomizers were determined in order to represent the
194 identical E as for the single-fluid atomizers to allow for unbiased comparison.

$$E = V_L(p_L + GLR \frac{\rho_L}{\rho_g} (p_g + p_b) \ln(\frac{p_g + p_b}{p_b})) \quad (7)$$

195 where p_g is the atomization gas overpressure and p_b is the pressure of the surrounding atmosphere.

196 The E for the single-fluid atomizers is calculated simply as the product of pressure and liquid volume
197 V_L .

198 To estimate the entrainment, the integral value of the entrained volume, IV_e can be calculated using
199 equation (8). The droplet size distributions need to be measured at various radial positions within the
200 spray, recording the cumulative volume distribution of droplets for each position. The droplet volume
201 contained in droplets smaller than the entertainment diameter is then determined as

$$IV_e = \frac{\sum r_{if} V_{e,i}}{\sum r_{if} i}, \quad (8)$$

202 where $V_{e,i}$ is the volume of liquid within the droplets smaller than the entrainment diameter evaluated
203 in the i -th position.

204 **2.4. Results**

205 This section presents the comparative performance of the atomizers, focusing on spray geometry,
206 droplet characteristics, and energy efficiency. It is important to note that the following figures
207 generally plot one measured output metric (e.g., SCA) against another (e.g., ID_{32}). This is done to reveal
208 the correlations and trade-offs inherent to each atomizer's design. Both metrics are dependent
209 outcomes of the specific operating conditions detailed in the Methods section. The range of droplet
210 sizes between 270 and 480 μm shown in the following figures corresponds to the lower and upper
211 limits of droplets suitable for our columns. Nonetheless, the whole measured range of produced
212 droplets is always shown for the sake of generalizability, as different columns have different droplet
213 size requirements, and the compared atomizers have a broad range of applicability.

214 **2.5. Spray Geometry and Hydraulic Performance**

215 The ability to control the SCA is critical for matching the spray to the reactor geometry. Figure 4 (left)
216 illustrates the SCA as a function of ID_{32} . This plot validates the primary goal of the custom atomizer
217 design: the HC-A and HC-B series produced two distinct and predictable SCA groups, approximately 15°
218 and 40° , respectively. This demonstrates that the atomizer constant, K , can be effectively used to
219 engineer a target SCA . In contrast, the FF atomizers exhibited a wider range of $SCAs$. The SH atomizer
220 is not shown, as its design produces a near-zero-degree spray with droplets falling vertically.

221 The C_d , a key design parameter that quantifies an atomizer's hydraulic throughput, is shown in Figure
222 4 (right). It relates the actual measured liquid mass flow rate to the theoretical maximum for a single-
223 phase liquid flowing through an ideal orifice of the same area. The results reveal two distinct
224 performance groups. All single-fluid atomizers demonstrated high throughput, with C_d values ranging

225 from 0.6 to 0.8. In contrast, the twin-fluid atomizers (EFF and IMP) exhibited significantly lower C_d
 226 values around 0.3. This is a consequence of the liquid throughput reduction in the two-phase flow at
 227 the exit orifice, which does not appear in the single-phase atomizers. For most atomizer types, C_d
 228 remained relatively constant across the tested operating conditions.

229

230 *Fig. 4. SCA (left) and C_d (right) of the measured atomizers as a function of droplet size. The vertical lines*
 231 *at 270 and 480 μm indicate the target droplet diameter range for optimal performance within the*
 232 *laboratory columns used in this study.*

233 2.6. Atomization Efficiency and Droplet Entrainment

234 The η_A and the risk of droplet entrainment represented by IV_e are key metrics for process efficiency
 235 and environmental safety. Figure 5 (left) reveals a notable trend: for most atomizers, atomization
 236 efficiency was highest when producing larger droplets at lower operating pressures and decreased as
 237 droplet size became smaller (at higher operating pressures). The single-fluid atomizers, particularly the
 238 FF and pressure-swirl types (HC, FC), achieved the highest η_A values, exceeding 2%. The twin-fluid
 239 atomizers demonstrated lower overall efficiency ($\eta_A < 2\%$), a direct consequence of the energy
 240 required to compress the atomization gas.

241

242 Fig. 5. The results of η_A (left) and IV_e (right) of the measured atomizers as a function of droplet size.

243 The potential for entrainment, quantified by IV_e , shows a strong power-law dependence on droplet
 244 size, as seen in Figure 5 (right). Atomizers producing the smallest droplets inherently pose the highest
 245 entrainment risk. The twin-fluid atomizers (EFF and IMP) showed the highest risk, with up to 30% of
 246 the spray volume contained in droplets smaller than the 270 μm entrainment threshold. Conversely,
 247 the single-fluid atomizers, especially when operated at lower pressures to produce larger droplets,
 248 kept the entrainment risk minimal ($IV_e < 5\%$).

249 Figure 6 (left) directly plots the trade-off between atomization efficiency and entrainment. The
 250 pressure-swirl atomizers (HC, FC) and FF occupy a favorable region, demonstrating the ability to
 251 achieve high efficiency ($\eta_A > 2\%$) while maintaining near-zero entrainment risk.

252

253 Fig. 6. The dependence of droplet entrainment on η_A (left) and IRSF as a function of droplet size (right).

254 **2.7. Droplet Size Distribution**

255 The uniformity of the DSD is quantified by the *IRSF*, where a lower value indicates a more
256 monodisperse spray. Figure 6 (right) shows that the SH atomizer produced the most uniform spray
257 (*IRSF* \approx 0.5), consistent with the expected behavior of plain-orifice atomization in the Rayleigh breakup
258 regime. The other single-fluid atomizers produced relatively narrow DSDs, with *IRSF* values between
259 1.0 and 1.5. In contrast, the twin-fluid atomizers produced significantly wider, more polydisperse
260 sprays (*IRSF* from 1.7 to 3.2), a characteristic inherited from their typical use in combustion applications
261 where a wide DSD can be advantageous.

262 **2.8. Specific Energy Consumption**

263 To provide a practical measure of operational cost, the specific energy consumption required to
264 atomize a unit mass of liquid was calculated. The calculation can be performed according to equation
265 (7), where the absolute volume V_L is substituted with specific volume v_L in m^3/kg . The comparison
266 (Figure 7) shows the superiority of SH and FF atomizers. HC and FC atomizers were just slightly worse,
267 consuming between 123 and 294 J/kg. EFF atomizers consumed between 250 and 757 J/kg and IMP
268 361 to 894 J/kg. Although this energy consumption might seem small for the laboratory columns with
269 a single atomizer and low flow rates, simple multiplication by the number of atomizers and actual
270 solvent flow rates required in the industrial columns emphasizes the need for careful consideration of
271 this aspect.

272

273 *Fig. 7. The comparison of specific energy consumption for all configurations of tested atomizers.*

274 **2.9. Uncertainties**

275 Uncertainties were estimated as type A uncertainties from repeated measurements. The reported
 276 uncertainties for the key integral parameters are $\pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$ for ID_{32} , ± 0.08 for $IRSF$, and $\pm 2.3^\circ$ for SCA .

277 **2.10. Operational Observations**

278 During testing, notable differences in operational robustness were observed. The FF atomizers, despite
 279 their high efficiency, were highly sensitive to impurities in the liquid, with minor particle deposition on
 280 the orifice causing significant spray pattern distortion. The SH atomizer also exhibited orifice clogging.
 281 In contrast, both twin-fluid atomizers (EFF and IMP) and the pressure-swirl atomizers (HC and FC)
 282 performed reliably without any clogging issues throughout the test campaign.

283 3. Discussion

284 The results showed that there is no universally "best" atomizer for spray-column carbon capture;
285 rather, the optimal choice depends on a complex balance of competing performance metrics. A
286 significant contribution of this work is the successful demonstration that through deliberate
287 engineering, equipment can be tailored to overcome the operational constraints of a specific
288 application. The custom-designed HC atomizers achieved their primary design goal: providing tailored
289 spray cone angles (15° and 40°) independent of the liquid flow rate. This capability is a critical step
290 towards designing more efficient and compact reactors, as it allows the spray geometry to be precisely
291 matched to the reactor dimensions, minimizing detrimental effects like wall-wetting and flue gas
292 bypass that reduce overall capture efficiency.

293 When considering single-fluid atomizers, a clear trade-off emerges between peak performance and
294 operational robustness. The FF atomizers demonstrated the highest atomization efficiency and lowest
295 specific energy consumption, making them an attractive option from an energy standpoint.
296 Interestingly, the results also showed a counterintuitive trend where efficiency did not increase with
297 higher energy input. This is because at the higher operating pressures needed to produce the smallest
298 droplets, a larger fraction of the input energy is converted into the kinetic energy of the liquid rather
299 than being used to create new surface area. This highlights a point of diminishing returns in the
300 atomization process.

301 Despite the good performance of FF from an energetic point of view, its sensitivity to clogging presents
302 a significant operational risk in industrial environments where sorbents may contain impurities.
303 Similarly, while the SH atomizer produced the most uniform droplets, its susceptibility to clogging,
304 together with large droplet size, restricts its applicability to systems with high flue gas velocities. The
305 pressure-swirl atomizers (HC and FC) represent a compelling compromise, offering high hydraulic and

306 atomization efficiencies, low entrainment risk, and robust, clog-free operation, making them strong
307 all-around candidates for reliable, long-term industrial deployment.

308 Twin-fluid atomizers (EFF and IMP) present a different set of trade-offs. Their ability to generate the
309 finest droplets is advantageous for maximizing the gas-liquid interfacial area, and their inherent design
310 makes them highly resistant to clogging, even with viscous or contaminated liquids. However, these
311 benefits come at a steep cost. Their specific energy consumption was up to three times higher than
312 that of the top-performing single-fluid atomizers, representing a major energy penalty at the process
313 scale. Furthermore, they produced a highly polydisperse spray with a significant volume of fine
314 droplets, leading to a substantial entrainment risk of up to 30%. While the use of compressed air may
315 be feasible in some industrial settings, the combined penalty of high energy cost and the need for more
316 robust de-misting systems must be carefully weighed.

317 The importance of the DSD and its link to entrainment is crucial for applications in carbon capture
318 columns. A narrow DSD, as produced by the SH and FF atomizers, is highly desirable as it ensures
319 predictable droplet trajectories and more uniform mass transfer rates, leading to better process
320 control. The wide DSD of the twin-fluid atomizers means that even when the average droplet size
321 (represented here by ID_{32}) is within an acceptable range, a significant number of small, entrainable
322 droplets are still produced. This necessitates the use of downstream demisters or droplet separators,
323 which not only add capital cost but also increase the overall system pressure drop, impacting
324 operational expenditure. Therefore, selecting an atomizer with a low IRSF can simplify the overall
325 process design and improve net energy efficiency.

326 To visually summarize these complex, multi-parameter trade-offs, the performance of each atomizer
327 type is consolidated in a normalized radar chart (Figure 8). To facilitate the fair comparison, each
328 performance axis in the chart has been scaled from 0 to 1 based on the measured data, where a score
329 of 1 represents the most desirable outcome (e.g., highest efficiency, lowest entrainment, lowest

330 energy use). This chart provides a direct comparison of the relative strengths and weaknesses of each
331 atomizer design.

332 Finally, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study and suggest directions for future
333 work. The performance characteristics were evaluated using water as a surrogate fluid. While this
334 provides a valid baseline for comparing primary atomization, future studies should investigate
335 performance with real sorbents to fully account for the effects of higher viscosity and potential for
336 fouling over long-term operation. Furthermore, while this work provides essential data on individual
337 atomizer performance, the next step is to understand system-level interactions. Computational Fluid
338 Dynamics (CFD) simulations should be performed for optimizing the arrangement of multiple
339 atomizers within a column and for modeling the complex interplay between spray dynamics, gas flow,
340 mass transfer, and solvent evaporation. Such simulations, grounded by the experimental data provided
341 here, can bridge the gap between component-level design and full-scale process optimization.

342

343 *Fig. 8. Comparison of key performance characteristics for different atomizer types*

344 **4. Conclusions**

345 This study highlights the complex and multifaceted nature of atomizer selection for the design of
 346 optimized spray-column-based carbon capture systems. There is no single ideal atomizer, as each type
 347 demonstrates distinct trade-offs among η_A , DSD, SCA , IV_e , and operational factors. The principal finding
 348 is that single-fluid pressure atomizers, specifically SH, pressure-swirl (HC, FC), and flat-fan (FF) types,
 349 offer the most balanced and energy-efficient performance for this application.

350 Our work successfully demonstrates that key geometric parameters, such as the atomizer constant K ,
 351 can be used to engineer equipment to meet specific process requirements, such as achieving an

352 optimal spray cone angle. This methodology enables tailoring the spray geometry to the reactor
353 dimensions to minimize sorbent loss from wall-wetting and improve overall capture efficiency.

354 While twin-fluid atomizers (EFF, IMP) produce the finest droplets, their high specific energy
355 consumption (up to 900 J/kg) and substantial entrainment risk (up to 30% of spray volume in
356 entrainable droplets) make them less practical for large-scale post-combustion capture systems. In
357 contrast, the top-performing single-fluid atomizers achieve high atomization efficiency ($\eta_A > 2\%$) with
358 minimal entrainment risk and significantly lower energy demand (< 300 J/kg). The final selection
359 hinges on a trade-off between peak efficiency and operational robustness: SH and FF atomizers are
360 the most energy-efficient, while pressure-swirl atomizers provide superior resistance to clogging,
361 making them a more reliable choice for industrial environments.

362 The results provide the data required for the informed design and techno-economic optimization of
363 next-generation, high-efficiency gas-liquid contactors. Future work should leverage these findings to
364 validate performance with industrial amine sorbents and integrate these optimized atomizers into
365 pilot-scale systems to quantify the system-level gains in CO₂ capture rates and real-life operational
366 expenditure.

367 **Data Availability:** The measurement datasets required to reproduce these findings and also suitable
368 for CFD validation and modeling, are freely available on Zenodo at:
369 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18712679>.

370 **Acknowledgements:**

371 The authors gratefully acknowledge Elsa Baronet and Edi Nushi for their assistance in compiling the
372 table summarizing atomizer applications reported in the literature. The authors also acknowledge the
373 financial support from the project no 23-07722S funded by the Czech Science Foundation and the Brno
374 University of Technology specific research fund FSI-S-23-8192. During the preparation of this work, the
375 authors used the AI tool Gemini (Google Inc.) for language editing. After using this tool, the authors

376 reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the
377 publication.

378 **References:**

379 AMUNDSEN, Trine G.; ØI, Lars E.; EIMER, Dag A. Density and viscosity of monoethanolamine+ water+
380 carbon dioxide from (25 to 80) C. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, 2009, 54.11: 3096-3100.

381 BANDYOPADHYAY, Amitava and BISWAS, Manindra Nath, 2012. CO₂ capture in a spray column using
382 a critical flow atomizer. *Separation and Purification Technology*. Vol. 94, pp. 104–114.
383 DOI 10.1016/j.seppur.2011.11.039.

384 BELKA, Miloslav et al., 2025. Numerical modeling of CO₂ capture in a spray tower with aqueous
385 ammonia and full-cone atomizers. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*. p. 105405. DOI
386 10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2025.105405.

387 CHEN, Chongchong, et al. Construction of a theoretical model for fan nozzles with precise atomization
388 angles for plant protection. *Chemosphere*, 2022, 287: 132017.

389 KASHANI, Arash; PARIZI, H.; MERTINS, Karl-Heinz. Multi-step spray modelling of a flat fan
390 atomizer. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 2018, 144: 58-70.

391 CEJPEK, Ondrej, et al. Evaluation of Orifice Shape Design on Flat Fan Atomization. In: EPJ Web of
392 Conferences. EDP Sciences, 2024. p. 01006.

393 CEJPEK, Ondrej et al., 2023. Novel atomizer concept for CCS applications: Impinging effervescent
394 atomizer. *Separation and Purification Technology*. Vol. 311, p. 123259.
395 DOI 10.1016/j.seppur.2023.123259.

396 CEJPEK, Ondrej, et al. Pressure loss and droplet entrainment under spray absorber conditions.
397 *Separation and Purification Technology*, 2025, vol. 354, no. 8, p. 129339. DOI:
398 10.1016/j.seppur.2024.129339

399 CHEN, Wei-Hsin, HOU, Yu-Lin and HUNG, Chen-I, 2012. Influence of droplet mutual interaction on
400 carbon dioxide capture process in sprays. *Applied Energy*. Vol. 92, pp. 185–193.
401 DOI 10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.10.035.

402 CHO, Minki et al., 2018. Novel Spray Tower for CO₂ Capture Using Uniform Spray of Monosized
403 Absorbent Droplets. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. Vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 3065–3075.
404 DOI 10.1021/acs.iecr.7b05309.

405 DIMICCOLI, A., DI SERIO, M. and SANTACESARIA, E., 2000. Mass Transfer and Kinetics in Spray-Tower-
406 Loop Absorbers and Reactors. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. Vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 4082–
407 4093. DOI 10.1021/ie000137y.

408 FANG, Mengxiang et al., 2020. Emission and control of flue gas pollutants in CO₂ chemical absorption
409 system – A review. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*. Vol. 93, p. 102904.
410 DOI 10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.102904.

411 FU, Kaiyun et al., 2015. Experimental analyses of mass transfer and heat transfer of post-combustion
412 CO₂ absorption using hybrid solvent MEA–MeOH in an absorber. *Chemical Engineering Journal*.
413 Vol. 260, pp. 11–19. DOI 10.1016/j.cej.2014.08.064.

414 HADLOCON, L. S., 2014. Optimization of Ammonia Absorption Using Acid Spray Wet Scrubbers.
415 *Transactions of the ASABE*. pp. 647–659. DOI 10.13031/trans.57.10481.

416 HAMMAD, Farid A. et al., 2021. Internal two-phase flow and spray characteristics of outside-in-liquid
417 twin-fluid atomizers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*. Vol. 187, p. 116555.
418 DOI 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2021.116555.

419 JAVED, K.H., MAHMUD, T. and PURBA, E., 2010. The CO₂ capture performance of a high-intensity
420 vortex spray scrubber. *Chemical Engineering Journal*. Vol. 162, no. 2, pp. 448–456.
421 DOI 10.1016/j.cej.2010.03.038.

422 JEDELSKY, Jan et al., 2009. Development of an Effervescent Atomizer for Industrial Burners. *Energy &*
423 *Fuels*. Vol. 23, no. 12, pp. 6121–6130. DOI 10.1021/ef900670g.

424 JEDELSKY, Jan and JICHA, Miroslav, 2013. Energy conversion during effervescent atomization. *Fuel*.
425 Vol. 111, pp. 836–844. DOI 10.1016/j.fuel.2013.03.053.

426 KOLLER, M. et al., 2011. Test results of CO₂ spray scrubbing with Monoethanolamine. *Energy Procedia*.
427 Vol. 4, pp. 1777–1782. DOI 10.1016/j.egypro.2011.02.053.

428 KUNTZ, Jeffery and AROONWILAS, Adisorn, 2008. Performance of Spray Column for CO₂ Capture
429 Application. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. Vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 145–153.
430 DOI 10.1021/ie061702l.

431 LI, Xiaonian et al., 2003. Removal of Carbon Dioxide from Flue Gas by Ammonia Carbonation in the Gas
432 Phase. *Energy & Fuels*. Vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 69–74. DOI 10.1021/ef020120n.

433 LIM, Youngbok et al., 2013. Performance Characteristics of CO₂ Capture Using Aqueous Ammonia in a
434 Single-Nozzle Spray Tower. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. Vol. 52, no. 43, pp. 15131–
435 15137. DOI 10.1021/ie401981u.

436 MA, Shuangchen et al., 2013. Research on mass transfer of CO₂ absorption using ammonia solution in
437 spray tower. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. Vol. 67, pp. 696–703.
438 DOI 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2013.08.090.

439 MALY, M., SAPIK, M., CEJPEK, O., WIGLEY, G., KATOLICKY, J., JEDELSKY, J. Effect of spill orifice geometry
440 on spray and control characteristics of spill-return pressure-swirl atomizers. *Experimental Thermal and*
441 *Fluid Science*, 2019, vol. 106, p. 159.

442 NIU, ZhenQi, GUO, YinCheng and LIN, WenYi, 2010. Experimental studies on removal of carbon dioxide
443 by aqueous ammonia fine spray. *Science in China Series E: Technological Sciences*. Vol. 53, no. 1,
444 pp. 117–122. DOI 10.1007/s11431-010-0023-6.

445 NURAL, Ozan Ekin and ERTUNÇ, Özgür, 2018. PREDICTING THE PERFORMANCE OF PRESSURE-SWIRL
446 ATOMIZERS. *Atomization and Sprays*. Vol. 28, no. 6. DOI 10.1615/AtomizSpr.2018021140.

447 PINILLA, E. A., DÍAZ, J. M. and COCA, J., 1984. Mass transfer and axial dispersion in a spray tower for
448 gas-liquid contacting. *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*. Vol. 62, no. 5, pp. 617–622.
449 DOI 10.1002/cjce.5450620507.

450 QING, Z., YINCHENG, G., and ZHENQI, N., 2011. Experimental Studies on Removal Capacity of Carbon
451 Dioxide by a Packed Reactor and a Spray Column Using Aqueous Ammonia. *Energy Procedia*, 4, pp.
452 519–524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.01.083>.

453 SEYBOTH, Oliver et al., 2014. Development of a Spray Scrubbing Process for Post Combustion CO₂
454 Capture with Amine Based Solvents. *Energy Procedia*. Vol. 63, pp. 1667–1677.
455 DOI 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.176.

456 STOLAROFF, Joshua K., KEITH, David W. and LOWRY, Gregory V., 2008. Carbon Dioxide Capture from
457 Atmospheric Air Using Sodium Hydroxide Spray. *Environmental Science & Technology*. Vol. 42, no. 8,
458 pp. 2728–2735. DOI 10.1021/es702607w.

459 TAMHANKAR, Y. et al., 2015. Spray absorption of CO₂ into monoethanolamine: Mass transfer
460 coefficients, droplet size, and planar surface area. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*. Vol. 104,
461 pp. 376–389. DOI 10.1016/j.cherd.2015.08.012.

462 TANIGUCHI, Izumi and ASANO, Koichi, 1992. Experimental study of absorption of carbon dioxide from
463 carbon dioxide-air gas mixture by water spray. *JOURNAL OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING OF JAPAN*.
464 Vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 614–616. DOI 10.1252/jcej.25.614.

465 TANIGUCHI, Izumi, TAKAMURA, Yusuke and ASANO, Koichi, 1997. Experimental Study of Gas
466 Absorption with a Spray Column. *JOURNAL OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING OF JAPAN*. Vol. 30, no. 3,
467 pp. 427–433. DOI 10.1252/jcej.30.427.

468 THIELICKE, William and STAMHUIS, Eize J., 2014. PIVlab – Towards User-friendly, Affordable and
469 Accurate Digital Particle Image Velocimetry in MATLAB. *Journal of Open Research Software*. Vol. 2,
470 no. 1. DOI 10.5334/jors.bl.

471 TURPIN, A. et al., 2008. Experimental study of mass transfer and H₂S removal efficiency in a spray
472 tower. *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*. Vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 886–892.
473 DOI 10.1016/j.cep.2007.02.002.

474 WANG, Penghui and DAI, Gance, 2018. Synergistic effect between spraying layers on the performance
475 of the WFGD spray column. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Chemical Engineering*. Vol. 13, no. 6, p. e2266.
476 DOI 10.1002/apj.2266.

477 XU, Yin et al., 2021. Modeling and analysis of CO₂ capture by aqueous ammonia + piperazine blended
478 solution in a spray column. *Separation and Purification Technology*. Vol. 267, p. 118655.
479 DOI 10.1016/j.seppur.2021.118655.

480 YEH, Norman K. and ROCHELLE, Gary T., 2003. Liquid-phase mass transfer in spray contactors. *AIChE*
481 *Journal*. Vol. 49, no. 9, pp. 2363–2373. DOI 10.1002/aic.690490912.

482 ZAREMBA, Matous et al., 2017. Low-pressure twin-fluid atomization: Effect of mixing process on spray
483 formation. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIPHASE FLOW*. Vol. 89, pp. 277–289.
484 DOI 10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2016.10.015. Web of Science ID: WOS:000393002400020

485 ZIMMERMANN, Simone et al., 2017. Experimental Studies on Spray Absorption with the Post
486 Combustion CO₂ Capture Pilot-Plant CASPAR. *Energy Procedia*. Vol. 114, pp. 1325–1333.
487 DOI 10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1252.

488 RIZK, N. K. and LEFEBVRE, A. H., 1986. Prediction of velocity coefficient and spray cone angle for simplex
489 swirl atomizers. In: *ICLASS-85; Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Liquid Atomisation*
490 *and Spray Systems, London, England, July 8-10, 1985. Volume 1*. London: Institute of Energy, pp.
491 IIIIC/2/1–IIIIC/2/16.

PREPRINT

Tab. A1. The overview of applications of atomizers in carbon capture spray columns reported in the literature.

	D	H	V_g	V_L	U_g	$C_{g,in}$	sorbent	C_L	T_{in}	atomizer type	D_{32}	SCA
Unit	m	m	L/min	L/min	m/s	vol %	-	wt %	°C		µm	°
Cho et al., 2018	0.115	1.0, 1.5	13 - 36	0.2 - 0.3	0.2 - 0.5	15	NH ₃	8	25	SH	310	0
Qing et al., 2011	0.1	0.5	10, 20, 28	0.13-0.4	0.02 - 0.06	5-15	NH ₃	2, 8, 16	20-55	PA	30-40	NS
Lim et al., 2013	0.1, 0.2, 0.3	1	25 - 150	0.2 - 0.65	0.053	6.6 - 35.7	NH ₃	5 - 20	15	PS	44 - 115	50, 58, 61
Xu et al., 2021	0.15	1.5	75 - 150	1.5, 2, 3	0.09 - 0.14	15	NH ₃ + PZ	2.5, 5,10 (NH3); 0, 0.1, 0.4 (PZ)	30 - 45 (gas) 20 - 45 (liquid)	PS	NS	NS
Tamhankar et al., 2015	0.2027	3.7	320	0.76, 1.14	0.17	12	MEA	30 - 40	30	FC	120 - 200	53
Kuntz & Aroonwilas, 2008	0.1	0.55	52 - 240	up to 1.35	0.004 - 0.2	0 - 45	MEA	18 - 43	25	PL	NS	90
Zimmermann et al., 2017		5	2 000		0.3	15	MEA	30	30 - 70 (gas), 40 (liquid)	FC	1600, 1100	90, 45
Ma et al., 2013	0.055	0.35	3.33 - 6.67	1.5 - 3	0.02 - 0.05	10 - 20	NH ₃	1 - 7	20 - 50 (gas)	NS	NS	NS
Javed et al., 2010	0.1	1.25	50 - 800	2 - 20	0.11 - 1.7	2.5	NaOH	5	20	PS	156 - 290	30, 15
Bandyopadhyay & Nath Biswas, 2011	0.1905	2	200 -372	0.67 - 1.87	0.11-0.22	0.7 - 2.5	NaOH	1.08 - 1.24	23	EFF	72 - 1408	NS
Seyboth et al., 2014	0.37	5	2 000	9.83	0.3	2.5 - 15	MEA	30	40	FC	1 600	90
Koller et al., 2011	0.15	0.2	2 667	max 33.3	2.5	14	MEA	30	40	NS	NS	NS
Hadlocon et al., 2014	0.356, 0.457, 0.61	2.12, 1.65	12000-32000	0.21 - 1.65	2, 3, 4, 5, 5.3	0.001 -0.04 NH3	H ₂ SO ₄	0 - 1	12, 23, 30	FC, HC	50, 100, 200	NS
Pinilla et al., 1984	0.45	0.95	858-1340	13.5 - 20.0	NS	0.7	bicarb solution	NS	NS	FC	3400 - 3800	NS
Stolaroff et al., 2008	1.17	3.8	NS	4	0.4	NS	NaOH	1.4 - 5.32	15, 19, 20	FC	100 - 400	NS
Tamhankar et al., 2015	0.2027	3.7	350	6300 - 15900	0.17	0.045 - 0.065	NaOH	0.4	30	FC	120 - 200	53
Niu et al., 2009	0.12	1.3	7.6 - 24.7	0.12 - 0.2	0.01 - 0.04	7 - 15	NH ₃	0.8-10	28-38	NS	30 - 40	NS
Taniguchi & Asano, 1992; Taniguchi et al., 1997	0.18	0.5	up to 24	4 - 12	NS	0.05 - 1.0	NaOH	NS	11 (gas); 9-20 (liquid)	FC	137 - 185	NS
Dimiccoli et al., 2000	NS	0.27	NS	1.18	NS	NS	NaOH	NS	46	FC	136	60, 90, 120
Turpin et al., 2008	0.15	1	10 - 30	0.04 - 0.48	0.01-0.03	0.4	NaOCl	NS	NS	FC	NS	NS
Li et al., 2003	0.063	0.18	0.167-0.670	0.335	NS	15	NH ₃ , NH ₄ HCO	NS	40	NS	NS	NS
Chen et al., 2005	0.1	0.7	11	0.031	NS	5-20	NaOH, DEA, Ca(OH), TEA	2-20	100 - 250	NS	NS	NS
Yeh and Rochelle, 2003	0.91	1.2	NS	7.8-540	NS	NS	NaOH	0.4	NS	HC	NS	61 - 73

NS – not specified; PA - pressure atomizer; PL – plate spray atomizer; PS – pressure-swirl atomizer; in. – initial

D diameter of the spray column; H height of the spray column; V_g volume flow rate of the flue gas; V_L volume flow rate of the liquid, U_g gas velocity; $C_{g,in}$ initial concentration of CO₂ in the flue gas; C_L liquid solution concentration; T_{in} initial temperature

495 Not to scale

496 Fig. A1. Schemes of basic types of atomizers used in the past studies (a) plain-orifice pressure atomizer,
 497 (b) airblast atomizer, (c) impact spray atomizer, and (d) spiral atomizer. Illustrations at the bottom
 498 show the resulting spray pattern typical for each atomizer.

499

500 Fig. A2. A scheme of the showerhead (SH) atomizer.

501

502